

Generative AI as a Catalyst for Collaborative Knowledge Management: Impacts Across Individual, Intra, and Inter-Organizational levels

Abstract. As organizations navigate through complex and collaborative digital environments, Generative AI (GenAI) emerges as a transformative force for Knowledge Management (KM) processes. This paper highlights how GenAI technologies impact collaborative KM processes across individual, intra-organizational, and inter-organizational levels within the evolving paradigm of Industry 5.0. Through a literature review, the study explores how GenAI augments human cognition, enhances knowledge creation and sharing, and fosters organizational adaptability and innovation. The findings highlight GenAI's potential as cognitive partner, streamlining information flows, and improving decision-making across collaborative networks. However, challenges such as over-reliance, ethical risks, and the decline of critical human skills are also discussed. Furthermore, the paper identifies the evolution and gaps in current literature on Collaborative Networks (CNs) regarding the integration of AI technologies. It contributes to the ongoing discussion of a socio-technical transformation and provides an overview for rethinking collaboration and social strategies in the GenAI era.

Keywords: Knowledge Management · Generative AI · Collaborative Networks · Collaboration · Industry 5.0

1 Introduction

In today's dynamic and often volatile business environments, organizations are increasingly motivated to engage in collaborative processes to enhance their agility and resilience [1], [2], [3], [4]. Considering the emergent technological evolution, organizations aim to reinvent themselves and rapidly adapt to unexpected external and internal challenges by enabling digital transformative technologies capable of enriching various levels of those collaborative organizational processes [4]. Cognitive-enhanced technologies, such as Generative AI (GenAI), offer new opportunities for companies to evolve business processes, collaboration, and how information and knowledge are managed. In the context of Collaborative Networks (CNs), [5] suggested that collaboration is crucial for companies to thrive and achieve high levels of competitiveness. The general definition of a collaborative network (CN) comprises diverse, autonomous, and geographically distributed entities — ranging from organizations to individuals — that vary significantly in their operational environments, cultures, social capital, and goals towards a common understanding of the significance of network members collaborating together to achieve better results while supported by

computer network [5]. As ICT progresses and industrial paradigms metamorphose from i4.0 to i5.0, collaborative networks must accompany this evolution to a fifth generation that places the human worker at the centre of the technological evolution, bringing the i5.0 ideals of human-centricity, resilience, and sustainability to this vision [6, 7]. This evolution opens the discussion about how the adoption of emerging technologies brings new ways of collaboration by focusing on human-centred goals, augmenting human workers' capabilities in CNs processes and procedures, such as decision-making [7]. Thus, GenAI presents a unique capability to transform information and knowledge within organisations, critical to individual, intra-, and inter-organisational collaborative processes. Its ability to automate repetitive tasks, generate personalised insights, and facilitate new forms of learning presents a promising revolution for knowledge management and collaboration [8], [9], [10]. Knowledge Management comprises four basic processes: knowledge creation, knowledge storage and retrieval, knowledge transfer, and knowledge application [10], [11]. These four processes are concerned with optimising how knowledge is managed, which, with the support of technologies such as GenAI, a synergy between them can be created to facilitate and improve individuals, organisations, and collaboration. For instance, human workers have inherent cognitive limitations in information processing, memory, and recall; in contrast, GenAI presents unlimited possibilities for overcoming those limitations [10]. In knowledge creation, GenAI acts as a co-creator, enhancing information processing and cognitive functions, “synthesizing new knowledge by merging, categorizing, aggregating, and summarizing explicit knowledge” [8], [10]; for knowledge storage and retrieval, it can automate tagging and indexing for efficient access [8]; for knowledge transfer and sharing, it can facilitate personalized learning and disseminate specialized knowledge; and for knowledge application, it can provide real-time insights for improved decision-making [12]. These are some of the potential impacts that GenAI can contribute to KM processes and collaboration.

The main contribution of this paper is to characterise the potential applications of the GenAI technology in collaborative knowledge management processes within organisations. Through a review of extant literature, an overview of potential impacts of this technology is presented in a 3-level collaborative approach —individual, intra-organisational and inter-organisational. The evolving 5.0 paradigm, with its focus on human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience, combined with the increasing complexity of organisational environments and the emergence of human-like technologies such as Generative AI, reinforces the critical need to review current theory and empirical findings. Such a review is essential for fostering a deep understanding of these elements, achieving efficiency across organisational processes, augmenting and ameliorating human-machine collaboration and preventing future disruptions.

2 Methodology

This paper aims to address these critical areas through the following research questions:

RQ1: How do Generative AI technologies impact collaborative knowledge management processes across individual, organizational, and inter-organizational levels within evolving digital environments?

RQ2: What are the gaps in the Collaborative Networks (CNs) literature considering the evolution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies, particularly Generative AI?

Methodologically, this paper is based on a literature review. The search for relevant literature was primarily conducted across Scopus, Google Scholar, AIS library, Emerald, and Springer databases. Besides, for the purpose of this review, an exploration of the last five-year PRO-VE proceedings was made to encounter more papers in the CNs discipline while interacting with emergent technologies. A set of targeted expressions was employed, including:

("Generative AI" OR "GenAI" OR "GAI") AND "human-ai collaboration"
("knowledge management" OR "KM") AND ("Generative AI" OR "GenAI" OR "GAI")
("knowledge management" OR "KM") AND "collaborative networks"
"industry 5.0" AND ("Generative AI" OR "GenAI" OR "GAI")
"industry 5.9" AND "collaborative networks"

After an explorative search, approximately 120 papers were gathered. It is important to mention that some of this research was already developed in the light of a current master's degree dissertation about the impact of Generative AI on knowledge management processes within organizations, which already funded some of the articles for this paper. At the same time, natural language expressions were used on Semantic Scholar to retrieve articles in the relevant fields. During this process, the abstracts, results, and conclusions were reviewed to diminish the number of papers that could contribute to the presented research questions, leading to the 60 papers that were analysed for this research.

3 Collaboration in Knowledge Management

Knowledge Management (KM) is fundamentally concerned with the processes and infrastructure used to effectively generate, share, distribute, and apply organisational knowledge [11]. As time and technology advanced, organisations started to be viewed as places where knowledge resides and where the interaction between systems and culture is crucial for knowledge to be treated as an important organisational asset to enhance collaborative business processes [8] [17]. Managing knowledge contributes to better decision-making, problem-solving, creative and innovative processes, which, consequently, impact competitiveness at different levels [18]. Collaboration is fundamental to KM, not an optional extra; it is inherent to its core functions and deeply integrated within its processes. It requires that partners work together — a collective action — towards a common organisational goal and purpose [19]. Thus, KM involves complex, dynamic interactions among individuals, teams, and external partners to transform information into actionable insights and foster innovation [11]. In this evolving digital transformation, characterised by vast and complex data and

information flows, it is paramount that information arrives at the right people at the right time [20]. Knowledge management has three characteristic elements: people, processes, and technology. People, the most important element, produce knowledge and contribute to its success; processes address the actions related to the KM processes; finally, technology that supports people and processes, assisting the accessibility of knowledge at any given moment. For instance, the evolution of ICTs serves as a robust pillar for organisations to improve KM processes and take the best out of their information and knowledge assets [20]. In the context of CNs, collaboration boosts all the connected organisations to extend competitiveness by “integrating value-added activities, information, resources and knowledge between enterprises” [21]. This brings to the discussion the importance of current ICTs, such as Generative AI, with human-like capabilities, presenting a great potential to manage information and knowledge within organizations [10]. By aligning new digital technologies with the foundational tenets of KM and CNs, organisations create the possibility for new opportunities to grow, enhance business processes, increase competitiveness, and make more refined decisions. In the era of Industry 5.0, organisations see Generative AI as a catalyst that enables human-machine collaboration, opening a new perspective for workers who collaborate with GenAI to augment their capabilities while focusing on their well-being [22]. With GenAI as a potential transformative force in generating novel content, aligned with knowledge management processes focused on leveraging this content into an ever more valuable resource, collaboration between enterprises can start to imagine a brighter future.

4 Generative AI and Collaboration at Different Levels

The rapid evolution of advanced AI, particularly GenAI, plays a paramount role in the way organisations deal with information/knowledge and how business collaborative processes are performed [22], [23]. The capacity of GenAI to compress the information layer and create knowledge by processing large volumes of data [10] creates a variety of advancements in the organisational world, where most processes involve vast amounts of historical data and information that humans alone aren't able to easily process [13]. Unlike traditional AI, which mainly focuses on data AI-driven tasks such as predictions, classifications, or recommendations, GenAI is designed to create new and original content such as text, images, audios, videos, and code similar to the outputs of human intelligence by learning patterns from data [24].

Furthermore, the combination of i4.0 technologies with i5.0 ideals brings a new perspective on how organisations can interact with technologies while centring the focus on the human worker, through more sustainable and resilient actions [22] [25]. It's a way of leveraging individual and collective knowledge, as human workers and organisations hold the opportunity to augment cognitive abilities, automate routine tasks, and optimise business processes when collaborating with tools such as GenAI [22], [24], [26]. Considering this new paradigm, instead of humans working in parallel with machines, a high level of collaboration is proposed, where unique human capabilities are integrated with machine intelligent functions [12], [27] to develop a collaborative intelligent partnership [28], [29].

Since KM processes are directly engaged with the management of knowledge to effectively and rapidly respond to the organisation's processes and challenges, it seems that the employment of GenAI's technologies is aligned with the same commitment, leading to a potential improvement and assistance to those processes [8], [10]. Both aim to optimise how information and knowledge are handled to improve efficiency, productivity, and decision-making [10], [30]. Knowledge itself is considered a critical asset, distinct from data or information, as it is personalized information tied to human capabilities, experiences, beliefs, and education [11], [31], [32]. Thus, across the four fundamental KM processes — creation, storage and retrieval, transfer and sharing, and application —, enthralled in managing and leveraging this critical asset, GenAI, with its human-like abilities, introduces a significant impact in how knowledge is generated, codified, and disseminated through patterns from data [10], [14], [24]. What once was performed only by a human worker can now be co-performed with the aid of this technology, leading workers to more complex and strategic tasks instead [8], [33]. From unstructured to structured data sources, GenAI brings organisations “new opportunities to recombine and leverage a company's knowledge assets and transform knowledge work” [14]. These technological advancements have turned knowledge management “less costly, standardised, ubiquitous and more effective in responding to individuals' needs” [20].

We will examine the potential impacts of Generative AI (GenAI) across three levels of collaboration: individual, intra-organisational, and inter-organisational. These levels provide a structured framework for understanding how GenAI influences knowledge management (KM) in different collaborative settings. At the individual level, knowledge is created, shared, applied, and internalised by people; at the intra-organisational level, knowledge flows within an organisation—between individuals, teams, and departments; at the inter-organisational level, knowledge is exchanged across organisational boundaries through collaborative networks. This multi-level perspective offers a comprehensive view of GenAI's role in KM, recognising that knowledge processes operate at varying degrees of scale and complexity.

4.1 Individual Level

Generative AI plays a significant role in individual collaboration, particularly by augmenting workers' cognitive capabilities and facilitating their individual organisational processes [34]. The individual level refers to the collaboration between a human worker and the technology within an organisation, where AI systems are integrated into their daily workflows for task automation, augmented problem-solving, and enhanced decision-support [35]. As knowledge workers lavish a lot of time on repetitive tasks, gathering and synthesising information, GenAI appears as an aide that may partially or fully automate them, allowing workers to concentrate their time and skills on more complex and creative tasks, where human judgment is necessary [36]. In the *knowledge creation* process, GenAI and humans can function in perfect synergy, as one complements the other; humans with their unique characteristics of metacognitive and affective processes [37] and GenAI as a co-creator to generate or support creative processes such as brainstorming for creating ideas about new products

and services [33], product design and optimization [38], [39], and proposals of materials with desirable properties [14]. The capability of generating new content and insights is enormous, from being able to “synthesising new knowledge by merging, categorising, aggregating, and summarising explicit knowledge from varied sources” to even processing tacit knowledge (know-how) to create explicit knowledge [10]. GenAI can be seen as a “thinking partner”, where human workers interact with the system to obtain more information/knowledge that potentially aids their own knowledge. Newer and less-skilled workers can easily upskill and rapidly increase their learning curve in collaboration with GenAI tools through prompts in natural language [10] [26]. One important characteristic of GenAI is how it remembers the context and history of conversations with workers, which subsequently enhances the interaction between the worker and the system by offering personalised and contextual responses [10]. This is helpful for workers who desire to learn and retain knowledge without being involved in socialisation processes with high-skilled workers. On the other hand, as workers are able to access and internally retain knowledge with these tools, the lack of socialisation processes that enhance *knowledge sharing* can be affected, which is essential for knowledge to flow within the organization [10]. Also, questions about the quality of knowledge that workers are generating should be posed, as it might affect decision-making and operational optimisation — workers might blindly accept knowledge without questioning it or making an effort to internalise it [10]. Humans tend to take AI-generated information/knowledge as authoritative, leading to an over-reliance on the technology, which can potentially decline human critical thinking and problem-solving in the organization [8] [40]. In contrast, technology has a democratic role of making knowledge “accessible to everyone, anywhere, anything”, which empowers workers to individually grow and contribute to better business processes while also making KM processes less expensive [13]. As human-centricity ideals are a commitment for the current industrial revolution (i5.0), the relationship between human and AI technologies needs to be addressed, not as an afterthought, but as a way to elevate their role when interacting with the technology — “no one is more central to AI success than the workers who work at the front line of organizations and who integrate AI into their work practices” [29]. Thus, empowering human workers is paramount. For instance, in the manufacturing context, GenAI tools can act like virtual assistants on the factory floor where workers can interact with them too, “troubleshoot issues, access manuals, and receive real-time training, thereby enhancing their skills and productivity [41]. Individual learning is empowered, as knowledge workers can elevate their skills with personalised training and conversational learning. GenAI tools can support and improve *knowledge transfer*, facilitating the onboarding of new employees through interactive tutorials and simulations by analysing the user’s responses and role [10]. Younger workers might find it difficult to understand some expert knowledge, which can be transformed into easier terms and less complexity with GenAI [8]. This type of codification can also be useful in *knowledge application*, as workers, while simplifying, summarising, and generating scenarios through prompts, can effectively use knowledge for better decision-making by easily and rapidly retrieving it [10], [13], [29]. However, this comes with problems associated with intellectual property risks as workers may apply information/knowledge protected by

copyrights or leak confidential information from the firm [10]. There is a clear necessity to address themes such as “trust, transparency, safety and ethics” when studying human-AI collaboration [42]. Certainly, the outcomes of GenAI’s impact imply positive and transformational changes in the workers’ routine, but besides the technical capabilities and economic impact, it seems that research about the direct impact on individuals and how they perceive and deal with this technology is lacking [36]. The employment of these technologies needs to assure workers about their responsibility when interacting with it, “the relevance of human intelligence in AI-employee collaboration network” [16], as for a “successful collaboration, it is important to define clear roles and evaluate them continuously”. Collaboration with AI requires specific skills from workers — from understanding “the function of AI, the ability to formulate prompts and the ability to reflect and control behaviour and results” [43]. This relationship between humans and AI is characterised by challenging but empowering transformations that should be further expanded through research, so as to adapt these technologies to the workers’ needs and routines.

4.2 *Intra-organizational Level*

An intra-organisational process refers to activities and workflows that occur entirely within the horizon of a single organisation. These processes are focused on facilitating an “optimised” execution of tasks, involving information and knowledge flowing through at different levels of the organisational structure [44]. Naturally, as human workers are part of the organisational structure, the individual collaboration between humans and AI affects organisational business processes [15]. As [10] state, “organisations consistently generate, amplify, augment, and update both their tacit (unarticulated) and explicit (codified) knowledge resources through a variety of mechanisms and as knowledge flows through individuals, groups, and organisational artefacts”. The creation and dissemination of knowledge is enhanced by collaborative processes between groups of people and individual cognitive processes [10]. In relation to *knowledge creation*, GenAI can assist managers and collaborators in extracting insights from meetings into actionable insights. It can automatically generate “meeting notes with real-time transcription, provide meeting summaries, or extract information from videos”, which in combination with online collaborative tools can extract and analyse what was said in team meetings [14]. Also, as organizations store information and knowledge that is generated across individuals, projects, and processes, GenAI can improve *knowledge storage* by “providing automated tagging, categorization, and indexing of knowledge assets” and even “analyze the content, identify keywords, and assign appropriate metadata” which facilitates organization and the retrieval of knowledge to the workers [8]. Besides, considering GenAI’s automating capabilities, workers can rapidly access the organisation’s information and knowledge, making *knowledge retrieval* more efficient and easily searchable while also being able to generate summaries of the internal documents and other sources that are relevant for an organisational process [10]. The capacity to process large volumes of unstructured and structured data and understand users’ context and needs, tailoring retrieved information/knowledge [10], [29]. It learns from “individuals’ or teams’ recurrent KM

or communication practices (e.g., history of emails) and offers individualized solutions” — as an example, the system can learn which documents should store and what should be retrieved to the worker, “as well as what customer purchase history and supply-chain issues need to be retrieved for specific troubleshooting team meetings” [29]. If workers can retrieve personalised information/knowledge, personalised to each business situation, it is expected to increase productivity since the time lost to explore various documents and folders is decreased [29]. At the same time, the ability to process and understand natural language facilitates the process of searching, as queries can be more complex. Based on the query’s sentiment, GenAI is capable of retrieving knowledge that is more appropriate and efficient for the user’s needs [14]. Through Natural Language Processing (NLP) and interactive dialogue, codification of tacit knowledge to explicit knowledge, known as Externalisation on the SECI model by [32] GenAI, can assist in this codification process, turning it into an easily accessible and shareable format [14], [29]. Here, the role of the human is essential to translate their know-how knowledge to the machine, “alleviating the black box of AI, justifying decisions, training budding human experts, and garnering organisational support” [29]. Similarly to the individual level, contextual and personalised learning by coaching, in-depth explanations or actionable recommendations has an impact on the organisation, since workers can be more informed and learn faster, which also leads to more experienced workers who perform tasks more efficiently [10]. In the creation process, workers can enhance their creative cognitive process by exploring unconventional paths that didn’t cross their minds while thinking about innovation in products and services with the aid that GenAI immediately provides, fostering novel ideas and solutions within organizations [13], [38]. *Knowledge sharing* is a fundamental KM process in the intra-organisational level, directly connected to collaboration between different actors within the organisation — “an organisation capable of effectively sharing knowledge and information across various divisions possesses greater flexibility and responsiveness to deal with various needs in a timely manner” [30]. GenAI allows the sharing of resources and information by “enabling real-time information exchange across vital divisions, including R&D (Research and Development)” within an organization [30]. This technology can contribute with cross-departmental information sharing by constructing knowledge graphs, knowledge bases and also convert different modalities of data, leading to an effective integration and dissemination of internal and external information [45].

All these processes work together to enable effective *knowledge application*, where the combination of each GenAI impact increases the capacity of the worker to rapidly respond to an urgent matter; having access to stored knowledge through natural language interactions, responding to context-specific questions and instructions contributes to an effective use of GenAI-generated knowledge combined with critical thinking of the worker [8], [10], [14]. In the manufacturing field, GenAI can be integrated with sensors and IoT devices to collect and analyse data from production phases, enabling manufacturers to “optimise processes, minimise defects and enhance overall product quality” through its capability of “defect detection, root cause analysis and quality prediction”. This aligns with i5.0 sustainability goals as manufacturers can prevent product defects, which leads to waste reduction and economic benefits [46].

GenAI, aligned with other i4.0 technologies, can help workers to have access to information/knowledge generated by it and, as a result, will improve knowledge application. Still in the manufacturing industry, *knowledge transfer* is mentioned [46] with an example of personalised training from GenAI to aid less experienced operators in more complex production operations; GenAI acts as a tutor, generating scenarios and recommendations that will enhance knowledge internalisation and codification. This also leads to a more collaborative learning environment between operators and GenAI while also reducing costs in training and upskilling them [46]. These are some of the potential impacts that GenAI can offer in several areas and KM processes, but there are considerations that should be taken seriously, considering how these systems are managed, creating a necessity to find a balance between positive effects and reducing known challenges associated with this technology. According to [46] organisations, they must be involved in subjects such as ethics and transparency of GenAI, as workers are making significant and consequential decisions based on data, designs and decisions generated by it. Transparency of AI systems is essential to increase workers' trust in them. Attention to biases is also an important factor that directly impacts production processes in a negative way, which should be continuously evaluated. These challenges should not be forgotten as they might severely affect organisations' ability to excel in the employment of GenAI tools and take advantage of the positive effects.

4.3 *Inter-organizational Level*

The inter-organisational level refers to the interaction and relationships that occur between two or more distinct organisations. It's, in fact, collaboration between multiple organisations, working together towards common or compatible goals [5]. Inter-organisational collaboration is essential for independent organisations to reduce business risks, expand and reach into new markets, and enhance individual appeal to external entities [47]. Accordingly, collaboration might contribute to “increased productivity, agility to environmental changes, and innovation in value creation” [47]. Authors [5] describe Collaborative Networks (CNs) as a “variety of entities (e.g. organisations and people) that are largely autonomous, geographically distributed, and heterogeneous in terms of their: operating environment, culture, social capital, and goals”. Organisations can be part of different types of CNs, such as supply chains, virtual enterprises and organisations, to name a few [5]. As organisations understand the importance of collaborating with other entities to achieve success, the need for collaboration grows and motivates them to employ Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and computer networks for data and information exchange [19] — it impacts business performance and increases competitiveness [48]. Within these networks, information and knowledge are not secondary elements; they are critical resources and central to their processes and activities [48], [49]. As a result, KM is mandatory for organisations to deal with the flow of information and knowledge extracted from these inter-collaborative processes. One of the most important KM processes in CNs is *knowledge sharing*, as it comprises a lot of collaboration needed to disseminate knowledge across all network members. Individuals share tacit and explicit knowledge between network members, empowering innovation and helping workers to

receive knowledge from people with different experiences and skills [48], [50]. Authors [50] state that “enterprises of all sizes are collaborating in order to fulfil clients’ demands, meeting their needs concerning cost, time response and quality, integrating various distributed business processes, and making relevant information available to all entities”. Considering these particularities and goals of CNs, the employment of GenAI tools may potentially impart KM processes with the flexibility required to more efficiently derive value from knowledge generated by CNs. While some studies focused on understanding the impact of AI technologies on different types of CNs, such as supply chains that exist [51], [52], there is a lack of literature on how GenAI tools affect CNs. In the context of supply chains, specifically transportation and logistics, GenAI tools are already foreseen to contribute to optimizing operations and ensuring efficiency in logistics management as fleet managers might be able to “monitor vehicle health, track routes, and optimize delivery schedules” and these capabilities help with “route optimization, minimizing fuel consumption, and reducing transportation costs” [41]. These GenAI capabilities are intrinsically related to processes such as *knowledge creation* and *sharing*, since it acts as an information processor by analysing real-time data from various sources, synthesising complex information into actionable insights [10], allowing all stakeholders to obtain the information/knowledge necessary and accurately in a timely manner. At the same time, regarding the collaboration with other network members, customer communication can be improved by tracking shipments and receiving real-time updates through ChatGPT interfaces [41]. The knowledge generated by GenAI can be transformative and extremely impactful in supply chain management and inventory control [53]. Transformer-based generative models specifically demonstrated their strong capacity in predicting demand fluctuations, providing workers with knowledge about which production to schedule in real-time. Besides, the creation of supply chain scenarios and possible identification of different and more efficient routes for transportation and logistics leads organisations to mitigate disruptions and improve processes through knowledge created by GenAI [53]. As stated in [51], “AI-based systems facilitate collaboration among diverse stakeholders by creating a cohesive network where real-time data and predictive insights are shared seamlessly”, hence the importance of KM processes of *knowledge sharing* that improve decision-making and the dissemination of knowledge through collaborative networks [54]. As the market grows competitive and customers demand a variety of customised products, this brings a necessity for stakeholders to hold knowledge about the products and customers [54]; as GenAI can have access to information about production processes and sales, organisations can collaborate to secure good decisions and follow more sustainable actions.

Therefore, despite the lack of studies in the field, GenAI technology presents an opportunity to enhance collaboration between organisations, focused mainly on knowledge generation and sharing.

Table 1 synthesises this analysis.

<i>Collaboration Level</i>	KM Processes	GenAI Impact
<i>Individual</i>	Knowledge Creation	Augments human cognition, acting as a co-creator for new ideas, designs, and proposals.
	knowledge Storage and Retrieval	Provides personalized, contextual responses by remembering conversation history, and democratizes knowledge access, making it readily available for individual growth.
	Knowledge Transfer and Sharing	Accelerates upskilling and learning for less-experienced workers via natural language prompts, and facilitates onboarding and knowledge comprehension through interactive tutorials and simulations
	Knowledge Application	Enhances decision-making by rapidly simplifying, summarizing, and generating scenarios from knowledge.
	Knowledge Creation	Extracts actionable insights from meetings (e.g. notes, summaries, transcription) and fosters innovation by helping teams explore conventional ideas.
<i>Intra-organizational</i>	Knowledge Storage and Retrieval	Automates tagging, categorization, and indexing of knowledge assets; enables efficient and personalized retrieval of information from vast datasets (structured and unstructured) and assists in codifying tacit knowledge into explicit formats.
	Knowledge Transfer and Sharing	Enhances contextual learning for faster skill development and enables real-time information exchange across departments through knowledge graphs and multi-modal data conversion.
	Knowledge Application	Improves rapid response to urgent matters by providing immediate access to context-specific knowledge, optimizes manufacturing processes through defect detection and root causes analysis, and supports personalized learning for operators.
<i>Inter-organizational</i>	Knowledge Creation and Sharing	Processes real-time data from various sources to synthesize actionable insights for all stakeholders, enhance customer communication, optimizes logistics (e.g., route optimization, demand prediction), and facilitates seamless data and predictive insight sharing across collaborative networks.

5 Collaborative Networks (CNs) in the GenAI Era: Evolution and Gaps

The field of Collaborative Networks (CNs) has significantly evolved along technological advancements, particularly in the field of AI, leading to new paradigms like CN 4.0 and the current proposed CN 5.0 [7].

Organisations understand the relevance of integrating collaboration models to handle the frenetic and ever-changing market and high levels of competitiveness [7]. As mentioned above, CNs include individuals and organisations that are diverse and geographically dispersed, working together to achieve goals that would be impossible or prohibitively expensive if alone [5]. Since this synergy between entities is supported by digital systems, the emergence of ICTs present new routes for “improving connectivity and communication, increasing efficiency, enhancing collaboration, increasing ability of collecting, sharing, processing, and storing data, information, knowledge, improving global reach, improving resilience in crises and disruption, improving collective creativity, and enhancing real-time working” [7], [55], [56], [57]. From the 1980s, where collaboration networks were shaped and supported by traditional methods such as face-to-face meetings, phone calls, and emails; to the rise and adoption of digital technologies from the early 2000s such as instant messaging, online forums, and the evolution of internet; until current days, where various advanced technologies such as social media, Internet of Things (IoT), Cloud Computing, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) that support and enable collaboration and communication in innovative ways [7] — the rapid evolution was always accompanied by digital technologies. Through all the dynamic generation of collaborative networks, the fourth generation of CNs raises questions about the limited adoption of emerging technologies and how they interact with humans in a human-centred approach instead. These limitations lead the discipline to the CN5.0 generation, which focuses on humans’ needs and desires — not only the “users/participants/stakeholders of CNs, but also their co-designers, co-developers, and co-testers” — and the adoption of current digital technologies such as AI and ML. This adoption seems promising in improving “CNs processes and procedures (like decision-making, dispute resolution, network leadership and other critical processes), and better manage the flow of information and activities within the network” [7]. [58] shows that Large Language Models (LLMs) are revolutionising decision support systems through their capability of generating insights and suggestions, delivering rapid responses when they are needed. In the context of collaboration, it also analyses how advancements in AI are beneficial in helping entities (including humans and machines) to achieve their common goals through the implementation of “cognitive intelligence into machines to enable them to act as peers to humans in decision-making processes” [58], [59]. Additionally, [51] synthesise how the application of AI in areas such as SCM can be improved with “optimisation of supply chains, management of risk and security, management of knowledge, and automation of contract intelligence”. At the same time, affirm the necessity of contributing with more research in the design and impact of AI-based systems, since they’re complex socio-technical systems that need to be addressed, attending to factors such as human, social, and organizational [51]. Authors

[60] also state that there is a necessity for further research about AI development, but with a focus on “concrete values, their impact on work tasks or human level and, more generally, descriptions of values and impacts on society, organisations, or collaborative networks”. As a result, measures about i5.0 goals can be applied so organisations are adequately prepared to deal with the technology and its impact on workers and how much it impacts, positively or negatively, sustainable goals for the organisations. It seems that future research comprises the i5.0 objectives, the particularities and combination of technologies from i4.0, specifically GenAI, to understand how it will evolve while addressing complex societal challenges [7].

6 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper explores the transformative role of Generative AI (GenAI) on collaborative knowledge management (KM) processes across individual, intra-organisational, and inter-organisational levels. Through a literature review, it demonstrated that GenAI is not merely a supporting tool but a transformative actor, such as a co-worker, capable of reshaping how knowledge is created, stored, shared, and applied. At the individual level, GenAI augments cognitive capabilities, fosters personalised learning, and automates knowledge-intensive tasks. Within organisations, it enhances internal information/knowledge flows, supports real-time decision-making, and fosters creative processes. Across organisational boundaries, it enables more agile and intelligent supply chains, facilitates communication, and unlocks the potential for value co-creation among networked entities. However, the deployment of GenAI in collaborative KM is not devoid of challenges. Risks such as diminished critical thinking, ethical concerns, data privacy issues, and over-reliance on automated outputs highlight the need for responsible integration strategies.

For future work, it is important to deepen the research about Collaborative Networks (CNs) in relation to the employment of Generative AI technology to fully grasp how the discipline might evolve in the future, contributing to enhanced results in how network members collaborate with each other. In the Knowledge Management (KM) field, empirical findings of how GenAI impacts KM processes within organisations seem extremely relevant. Similarly, it is crucial that, in the process of GenAI integration within organisations, research of a socio-technical perspective where factors such as processes, people, organisational context, and other social aspects are considered along with the goals and objectives coming from Industry 5.0.

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